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Chemical mixture risk drivers and their heterogeneity in European freshwaters

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ABSTRACT

Chemical pollution of aquatic environments involves diverse substance combinations that can provoke combined biological and toxicological effects even when individual concentrations remain below effect thresholds. Multiple efforts are ongoing to better consider mixture effects in chemical safety regulation, but debate continues over whether a few substances drive aquatic mixture risks or whether a large heterogeneous set of drivers must be considered.

We employed a data re-use strategy to investigate the heterogeneity of chemical mixture risk drivers to aquatic species in Europe. Initially, we derived 201 risk-driving chemicals from a single measurement campaign, allowing driver comparisons between sites based on consistently measured substances.

We then extended our analysis to extensive chemical monitoring data of the NORMAN network, originating from different campaigns focusing on diverging substance sets measured at different times and locations. Data were aggregated quarterly and sites clustered per quarter according to measured substances. Using a robust definition of risk drivers (the most significant chemicals whose cumulative toxic units contribute $\geq 75\%$ of total risk), our study concludes that at least 580 different substances drive chemical mixture risks in European freshwaters, with high heterogeneity between locations. Notably, mixture risk drivers were species-specific, exhibited temporal variability, and belonged to different chemical use groups considered in various safety regulations. We also found that monitoring data gaps prevented more precise analysis, particularly regarding temporal variability.

These findings have important implications for future chemical monitoring strategies and mixture risk regulation in Europe, highlighting the complexity and heterogeneity of chemical mixture risks in aquatic environments.

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1. Introduction

Exposure to chemical substances of anthropogenic origin poses a significant threat to human and ecosystem health. The analysis of public inventories estimated that approximately 355 000 chemicals are registered for production and use, with approximately 69,000 chemicals in commerce globally (Wang et al., 2020). The production of chemicals has doubled from 2000 to 2015 (Persson et al., 2022) and is expected to double again from 2015 to 2030 (European Environment Agency, 2019; United Nations Environment Programme, 2019). Upon the release of chemicals into the environment, they occur as complex and varying mixtures, determined, e.g., in surface waters (Malaj et al., 2014; Finckh et al., 2022b, 2024), waste-water treatment plant effluents (Finckh et al., 2022a), biota (Schaap et al., 2023; Terzic et al., 2024; Byns et al., 2024), or human bodies (Huber et al., 2022; Braun et al., 2024; Ma et al., 2023; Engelhardt et al., 2025).

There is well-established evidence that exposures of humans and environmental organisms to chemical mixtures can provoke combined effects, even if individual compounds occur in concentrations that are below their individual effect thresholds (Altenburger and Greco, 2009; Carvalho et al., 2014; Braun et al., 2024). Chemical safety regulation, thus, should consider mixture effects (Kortenkamp and Faust, 2018). However, this consideration is limited in current regulatory frameworks such as REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals), Regulations on Plant Protection Products (PPR), or the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR) which are single substance-focused and consider mixtures only if they are intended (e.g., product formulations).

The European Water Framework Directive (WFD, European Commission, 2000), introduced to protect European surface waters, also considers the risks of chemicals individually for each pollutant. Although pollution in its known entirety is assessed in terms of its impact on the states of freshwater systems compared to other stressors as part of the WFD assessments, the respective numbers of chemicals considered in such assessments is much lower than those known to occur from monitoring studies (European Environment Agency, 2024).

While EFSA considers plant protection product (PPP) mixture effects via cumulative assessment groups, this pertains only to the maximum residue levels in food and feed, and does not extend to mixtures in environmental compartments. Finally, the joint occurrence of pharmaceuticals and their degradation products as mixtures in freshwater systems, which are of significant concern (Weichert et al., 2025), is not considered in the environmental risk assessment of pharmaceuticals. To better protect people and the environment from the combined effects of chemicals, the European Commission announced the European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) in 2020 (European Commission, 2020). Introducing a mixture allocation factor (Backhaus, 2023) into the REACH framework is one of the options currently being discussed as part of this initiative (Treu et al., 2024).

The announcement of the CSS triggered a debate about the need to explicitly adapt chemical regulations to accommodate the risks of mixtures (e.g., Herzler et al., 2021; Scholz et al., 2022). The question at the heart of this debate is whether many substances are driving mixture risk or whether only a few identifiable chemicals act as major risk drivers, so that individual regulations of these risk-driving chemicals would be sufficient.

Several recent studies have addressed this question, with divergent results. Rorije et al. (2022) analyzed cumulative environmental risks from unintentional mixture exposures in European freshwater ecosystems based on data from 1998–2016 retrieved from the NORMAN chemical surface water monitoring database (Norman EMPo-DAT). The authors assessed hazard using species sensitivity distributions (SSDs, Posthuma et al., 2019). Upon filtering, retaining substances where hazard data was available, and aggregating over 30-day intervals, they considered 206 substances at 1867 locations, amounting to 34 354 unique place–time combinations. The authors found that 39% of

the place–time combinations were at unacceptable risk due to mixture exposures and that 10% of substances accounted for 90% of the toxic pressure.

Spurgeon et al. (2022) investigated surface- and groundwater samples and detected 491 and 515 analytes in groundwater and surface water, respectively, with GC–MS, and 290 and 315 analytes, respectively, with LC-MS. Again, using SSDs as effect measures, and chemical concentrations obtained with the GC–MS measurements, the authors found 876 of 23 000 surface water locations with exceeding risk thresholds due to combined occurrence of chemicals. They showed that, on average, the most toxic chemical contributed $\geq 20\%$ to the calculated mixture risk in $> 99\%$ of all measured locations.

Also using the SSD approach, Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023) investigated monitoring data collected under the WFD and retrieved from the European Environment Agency's (EEA) Waterbase. Their analysis included 334 chemicals at 4664 locations, where they looked at the annual median and maximum concentrations. After removing metals, the authors concluded that 15 chemicals were the most frequently observed drivers of chemical mixture risk, which, when removed, would render 95% of place–time combinations not at risk. They mentioned that most of those 15 mixture-risk-driving chemicals were already banned or listed in various regulatory priority lists.

Briels et al. (2023) re-analyzed chemical occurrence data from the EauFrance database merged with data from a surfactant monitoring campaign. The authors removed metals referring to Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023) upon curation and monthly aggregation which resulted in 234 mixtures from 80 unique locations, including 13 surfactants and 1283 other chemicals. For computing hazard quotients, they used the SSDs of Posthuma et al. (2019) when available and predicted no effect concentrations (PNECs) using the PETROTOX model otherwise (Redman et al., 2017). The authors concluded that six chemicals, which did not include surfactants, drove the toxic pressure in 95% of the investigated chemical mixtures.

A study not using SSDs but hazard data from US EPA Ecotoxicology Knowledgebase (EcotoxDB, Olker et al., 2022) for algae, aquatic invertebrates, and fish to calculate chemical mixture risks was conducted by Weichert and colleagues who measured 472 chemicals and detected 192 of them at six locations in a small German river named Holtemme (Weichert et al., 2025). When empirical hazard data was missing, they supplemented these with AI-predicted effect concentrations calculated by TRIDENT (Gustavsson et al., 2024). The authors identified fish as the most sensitive species group and 21 chemicals as potential mixture risk drivers with individual risk quotients of $RQ_i > 0.2$. Most of these 21 chemicals were pharmaceuticals.

Finally, the European-wide study by Finckh et al. (2022a) measured 499 chemicals in 56 wastewater treatment plant effluent samples. From these effluents, chemicals are directly released into rivers and small streams. By applying three different mixture risk assessment approaches using different hazard data in each approach, namely SSDs, effect data from EcotoxDB for algae, aquatic invertebrates, and fish, and regulatory values, such as PNECs or environmental quality standards, and by comparing the results across all locations, they identified 32 mixture risk driving chemicals common across all risk assessment approaches. These included pharmaceuticals, industrial chemicals, and a remarkable proportion of pesticides and biocides, making up 66% of the total risk-driving chemicals.

In summary, the number of identified mixture risk driving chemicals based on chemical monitoring data and different types of hazard data seems small in the individual studies with little overlap between them. Furthermore, there are remarkable differences in those studies, that need to be considered. For example, Weichert et al. (2025) identified 21 risk driving chemicals investigating only six locations, while others found fewer chemicals, investigating thousands of locations. While all studies used an additive approach to add up individual compound risks to mixture risks, the workflows differed significantly in data preprocessing, including and treating temporal data, the source for

hazard and exposure data, and the precise definition of a risk driving chemical. Finally, not all studies publicly provide the data and analysis code used, hindering the results' reproduction.

In this study, by using a data re-use strategy, we aimed to shed light on the questions of how diverse and heterogeneous chemicals that drive mixture risks in freshwater bodies are and how many of them we have to deal with. Within the WFD, ecological status assessments rely on Biological Quality Elements (BQE), which include algae, invertebrates (e.g. crustaceans), and fish. In our study, we use these three BQE as representative species groups for assessing chemical mixture risks. We integrated two large chemical monitoring data sets, including measured chemical freshwater pollutants in Europe, with a large set of curated hazard data (Kramer et al., 2024). Results based on targeted monitoring data are always biased by the set of substances being measured. Therefore, we utilized a step-wise approach, starting with a dataset where the same chemicals were measured at all locations, which thus allows for direct comparison of risk-driving substances between locations. Finckh et al. (2024) provide chemical concentration data for 503 substances in 445 freshwater locations acquired in a single measurement campaign across Europe. Subsequently, we extended our analysis to a curated version of the Norman EMPODAT (Mutlu et al., 2025), an extensive collection of chemical monitoring data provided by the NORMAN network, comprising data for 3771 chemicals at 12 499 locations measured between 1998 and 2020. We ensured meaningful comparisons of locations and time points by employing quarterly aggregation of data and clustering of locations and time points based on similarities in the sets of measured chemicals. We demonstrate that a substantial list of chemicals drives chemical mixture risks across Europe, and that these chemicals exhibit significant heterogeneity between locations and temporal variability.

2. Methods and data

2.1. Data sources

We used two datasets containing measured environmental concentrations of chemical pollutants in European freshwater systems:

1. **Dataset I:** A structured and complete dataset compiled by Finckh et al. (2024), measuring the same set of substances across all sampling locations. Dataset I comprises measurements obtained in a single measurement campaign, using samples collected in different campaigns between 2015 and 2021.
2. **Dataset II:** A curated and geospatially harmonized version of the NORMAN EMPODAT freshwater dataset, which we developed and published as part of our recent work (Mutlu et al., 2025). The curation process focused on standardizing spatial metadata to enable unambiguous identification of sampling locations, water bodies, and river basins. We also harmonized and corrected geospatial coordinates to ensure internal consistency and interoperability across data entries. Dataset II integrates measurements collected by the NORMAN network over the past 25 years, including various national and international monitoring efforts.

Dataset I provides a complete matrix of chemicals versus locations, with a consistent set of substances measured at all sampling sites with the same analytical method. In contrast, Dataset II is considerably sparser, reflecting the heterogeneity of historical monitoring activities, divergent sampling and analytical methods, and a variable chemical coverage across locations. Therefore, we used Dataset I to validate and illustrate the robustness of our analytical approach under idealized, uniform conditions before applying it to the more complex and heterogeneous Dataset II. Dataset I and II represent **exposure data**.

To enable the mapping of chemicals from Dataset II to further resources, we retrieved the Substance Database (susdat) as a .csv file from the NORMAN Database System (<https://www.norman-network.com/>

nds/) on April 24, 2024. The file contained 120 556 entries, including substance names and various chemical identifiers (e.g., CAS numbers, SMILES, InChIKeys). We refer to this dataset as **chemical_data** in the following. Chemical names shown in figures were taken directly from the NORMAN susdat database. These may differ from the standardized or preferred substance names used in the main text.

To complement the chemical_data, we enriched it with regulatory and functional annotations related to chemical safety and use. Specifically, we annotated substances registered under the European Union's REACH regulation (European Chemicals Agency, 2024b) and included product type information based on the Biocidal Products Regulation (European Chemicals Agency, 2024a). Additionally, we incorporated use group classifications derived from the work of Kramer et al. (2024). In cases where substances were associated with multiple use groups, we created compound labels that combine these categories (e.g., a substance annotated as both "IndustrialChemical" and "Pharmaceutical" was assigned the composite use group "Industrial-Chemical-Pharmaceutical").

We also used curated data for effect concentrations (EC) in aquatic species obtained from Kramer et al. (2024). These are concentrations at which the chemicals cause any phenotypic effects. They are either geometric means (geomean) of ECs derived from experimental data collected in the EcotoxDB or, if experimental data was not available, QSAR-based estimates for EC50/LC50 (effective or lethal concentrations). Kramer et al. (2024) have applied the VEGA QSAR models (Pedretti et al., 2021) *Algae acute [EC50] toxicity model (IRFMN) v. 1.0.1*, *Daphnia magna acute [EC50] toxicity model (IRFMN) v. 1.0.1*, and *Fish acute [EC50] toxicity model (IRFM) v. 1.0.1* to evaluate aquatic toxicity similar to the evaluations in Svedberg et al. (2023). Throughout this study, we refer to the collected effect concentrations for our substances of interest as **hazard_data**.

Additionally, we computed the *neutral fraction* of a substance to account for the bioavailable proportion of the substance when using QSAR-derived effect concentrations. The fraction of the neutral species of each chemical at pH 7 was determined using ACD GALAS (ACD/Percepta, ACD/Labs Release 2020.1.2).

2.2. Data preprocessing

We removed all samples from Dataset I where no concentration value for the given substance was provided.

Dataset II includes measurements of varying temporal resolution. To harmonize these data, we aggregated the Measured Environmental Concentrations (MEC_{clt}) for each chemical c (=substance), location, l and timepoint t by computing the median concentration per calendar quarter q :

$$MEC_{clq} = \text{median}(MEC_{clt} \{t : t \in q\}) \quad (1)$$

A substance c was considered *measured* at a location-quarter pair if its quarterly aggregated concentration was greater than or equal to zero ($MEC_{clq} \geq 0$), and *detected* if the value was strictly greater than zero ($MEC_{clq} > 0$). Substances for which no concentration value was reported at a given location-quarter pair were considered *not measured*.

We filtered the chemical_data table to retain only substances measured in Dataset II (i.e., excluding substances with no concentration values reported) for downstream integration.

We then merged Dataset I and the resulting subset of Dataset II, respectively, with the hazard_data and the calculated neutral fraction values to obtain a unified datasets for subsequent analysis.

2.3. Mixture risk assessment

To assess the risk posed by chemical mixtures to each species group, we first computed toxic units (TUs). For each measurement and species

group, the TU was calculated as the ratio between MEC_{clq} and the corresponding Effect Concentration (EC_{gc}):

$$TU_{gclq} = \frac{MEC_{clq}}{EC_{gc}} \quad (2)$$

Where TU_{gclq} denotes the toxic unit for the species group g , chemical c , location l , and quarter q , and EC_{gc} denotes the effect concentration of substance c for species group g . If the effect concentration was estimated using a QSAR model, the measured concentration was multiplied by the predicted neutral fraction prior to TU calculation to account for the bioavailable proportion of the substance.

For each species group g and location-quarter pair, we then computed the risk quotient (RQ) by summing the toxic units of all n detected substances (Backhaus and Faust, 2012):

$$RQ_{glq} = \text{sum}TU_{glq} = \sum_{c=1}^n (TU_{gclq}) = \sum_{c=1}^n \frac{MEC_{clq}}{EC_{gc}} \quad (3)$$

To evaluate whether the mixture risk was driven by one dominant substance or by multiple contributors, we calculated the contribution evenness metric $\text{ratio}TU_{glq}$, defined as the inverse of the maximum cumulative ratio (MCR) (Price and Han, 2011). We prefer to plot $\text{ratio}TU$ since it is distributed between 0 and 1, and thus independent of the scale of $\text{sum}TU$:

$$\text{ratio}TU_{glq} = 1/\text{MCR}_{glq} = \frac{RQ_{glq}}{\max_c (MEC_{clq}/EC_{gc})} \quad (4)$$

We defined locations with $RQ \geq 0.001$ as locations at risk to conservatively approximate chronic risks based on acute effect concentrations. Introducing a 1000-fold safety margin is in line with approaches commonly used to extrapolate from acute to chronic toxicity and to account for interspecies variation in ecotoxicology (e.g. Backhaus and Faust, 2012). This conservative cut-off facilitates precautionary risk assessment, though it should be noted that other studies may apply different thresholds, which can contribute to differences in reported mixture risks.

We defined the set of all locations where substances have been measured in quarter q as:

$$\mathcal{L}_q = \{l_1, \dots, l_n\} \quad (5)$$

with n denoting the total number of locations.

We defined the set of all *measured substances* \mathcal{M}_{lq} at location l and quarter q , as those substances c for which a concentration value was reported (i.e., $MEC_{clq} \geq 0$):

$$\mathcal{M}_{lq} = \{c \mid MEC_{clq} \geq 0\} \quad (6)$$

Further, we defined the set of *mixture risk drivers* D_{glq} for each species group g , location l , and quarter q as the smallest set of substances, ranked in descending order of TU_{gclq} , whose cumulative toxic units contribute at least 75% of the total mixture risk:

$$D_{glq} = \{c_1, \dots, c_k\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\} \text{ such that } \sum_{i=1}^k TU_{gc_i lq} \geq 0.75 \cdot RQ_{glq} \quad (7)$$

Hence, we summarized \mathcal{M}_{lq} and D_{glq} across all locations l as the unique sets of all measured substances \mathcal{M}_q per quarter and mixture risk drivers D_{gq} per species group and quarter as:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{gq} &= \bigcup_{l=1}^n D_{lgq} \\ \mathcal{M}_q &= \bigcup_{l=1}^n \mathcal{M}_{lq} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

For each driver, quarter, location, and species group, we computed the ratio between the TU of the driver and the sum of TU of all drivers at this location, which we termed the *driver importance*:

$$\text{driver importance}_{c_i, q, l, g} = TU_{g, c_i, l, q} / \sum_{c_j} (TU_{g, c_j, l, q}) \text{ such that } \{c_i, c_j\} \in D_{glq} \quad (9)$$

2.4. Clusters of locations with consistently measured drivers

The Norman EMPODAT dataset integrates measurements from multiple campaigns, resulting in heterogeneous chemical coverage across location-quarter pairs. Consequently, comparisons of mixture risk drivers across locations are only meaningful for those location-quarter combinations in which the respective substances were measured during the same quarter.

To identify *clusters of locations with similar sets of measured substances* in a given quarter q , we applied hierarchical clustering based on the Jaccard index computed from binary fingerprints indicating substance presence. Analogously, we identified *clusters of locations with similar sets of mixture risk drivers* by applying the same clustering procedure separately for each species group g , as risk is assessed in a species-specific manner.

2.4.1. Step 1: Binary fingerprint representation

We defined a binary fingerprint vector $\mathbf{f} \in \{0, 1\}^k$ for k substances, where a value of 1 at position i indicates that substance c_i is present, and 0 otherwise. For each quarter q , we generated two types of fingerprints: the *fingerprint of measured substances* \mathbf{f}_{lq} at location l , and the *fingerprint of mixture risk drivers* \mathbf{f}_{glq} for species group g at location l :

$$\mathbf{f}_{lq}^{m(i)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } c_i \in \mathcal{M}_{lq} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \mathbf{f}_{glq}^{d(i)} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } c_i \in D_{glq} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

2.4.2. Step 2: Similarity of driver sets

To quantify similarity between locations, we computed the Jaccard index, which is equivalent to the Tanimoto similarity for binary vectors, Jacc_{ijq}^m and Jacc_{ijq}^d for all pairs of binary fingerprints. These were calculated separately for measured substances (per quarter q) and for mixture risk drivers (per quarter q and species group g):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Jacc}_{ijq}^m &= \frac{|\mathbf{f}_{iq} \cap \mathbf{f}_{jq}|}{|\mathbf{f}_{iq} \cup \mathbf{f}_{jq}|} = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^k \min(J_{iq}^{m(r)}, J_{jq}^{m(r)})}{\sum_{r=1}^k \max(J_{iq}^{m(r)}, J_{jq}^{m(r)})} \\ \text{Jacc}_{ijq}^d &= \frac{|\mathbf{f}_{igq}^d \cap \mathbf{f}_{jgq}^d|}{|\mathbf{f}_{igq}^d \cup \mathbf{f}_{jgq}^d|} = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^k \min(J_{igq}^{d(r)}, J_{jgq}^{d(r)})}{\sum_{r=1}^k \max(J_{igq}^{d(r)}, J_{jgq}^{d(r)})} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Here, k denotes the number of substances considered in each case. This similarity metric represents the proportion of shared substances relative to the union of substances observed at locations i and j . In the case of mixture risk drivers, the calculation is species group-specific.

To derive distance matrices Δ_q^m and Δ_{gq}^d , we converted similarity scores to distances for all location pairs per quarter q (and per species group g in the driver-specific case):

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{ijq}^m &= 1 - \text{Jacc}_{ijq}^m \\ \delta_{ijgq}^d &= 1 - \text{Jacc}_{ijgq}^d \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

We then constructed the upper triangle of the corresponding distance matrices:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_q^m &= \left(\delta_{ijq}^m \right)_{\substack{i, j \in \mathcal{L}_q \\ i < j}} \\ \Delta_{gq}^d &= \left(\delta_{ijgq}^d \right)_{\substack{i, j \in \mathcal{L}_q \\ i < j}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

To enable efficient memory usage, all binary fingerprints were stored as sparse vectors, and similarity/distance matrices were implemented as sparse matrices. Pairwise comparisons were computed using optimized sparse matrix multiplication routines.

2.4.3. Step 3: Hierarchical clustering

Hierarchical clustering was applied to the distance matrices Δ_q^m and Δ_{gq}^d to identify clusters of locations for each quarter q (and for each species group g when based on driver similarity). We used a fixed tree cut-off threshold of $\theta = 0.5$ to extract clusters C of locations with similar sets of measured substances:

$$C_q^m = \left\{ C_{q,1}^m, C_{q,2}^m, \dots, C_{q,k}^m \right\}, \text{ with } C_{q,i}^m \subseteq \mathcal{L}_q \text{ and } \bigcup_{i=1}^k C_{q,i}^m = \mathcal{L}_q \quad (14)$$

Fig. 1. Example subset of a cluster with n locations and k substances. Rows represent locations l_i , and columns represent substances c_j . Color encodes substance status: blue for substances measured and identified as drivers, gray for substances measured but not identified as drivers, and white for unmeasured substances. A location is retained in the cluster only if all cluster drivers are measured (T = true), and removed otherwise (F = false). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Analogously, location clusters based on mixture risk driver similarity were defined for each calendar quarter q and species group g :

$$C_{gq}^d = \{C_{gq,1}^m, C_{gq,2}^m, \dots, C_{gq,k}^m\}, \text{ with } C_{gq,i}^m \subseteq \mathcal{L}_q \text{ and } \bigcup_{i=1}^k C_{gq,i}^m = \mathcal{L}_q \quad (15)$$

2.4.4. Step 4: Shrinking clusters to ensure all drivers were measured

Clusters C_{gq}^d were defined based on the similarity of mixture risk drivers. However, because driver identification depends on prior measurement, it is possible that some drivers were not measured consistently across all locations in a cluster. This could introduce artefactual heterogeneity due to missing data. To avoid this, we refined each cluster by removing locations in which one or more of the cluster's drivers had not been measured.

Assume a single cluster $C_{gq}^{d,(x)}$ derived from driver-based clustering. The complete set of mixture risk drivers for this cluster is defined as the union of all local driver sets:

$$D_{gq}^{(x)} = \bigcup D_{glq} \text{ with } l \in C_{gq}^{(x)} \quad (16)$$

A location l within the cluster is considered complete if all cluster drivers were measured there, that is:

$$D_{gq}^{(x)} = D_{glq} \cap \mathcal{M}_{lq} \quad (17)$$

We retained only those locations meeting this condition, resulting in reduced clusters:

$$\hat{C}_{gq}^{(x)} \subseteq C_{gq}^{(x)} \text{ with } l : D_{glq}^{(x)} = D_{glq} \cap \mathcal{M}_{lq} \quad (18)$$

Fig. 1 illustrates this filtering step.

The resulting shrunk clusters contain only locations with consistently measured drivers and were used to assess heterogeneity of driver composition between locations.

2.5. Identifying substances for which the measured environmental concentration may likely overestimate the freely dissolved concentration

Contaminants in surface waters partition between the freely dissolved phase, dissolved organic matter (DOM), and suspended particulate matter (SPM). Only the freely dissolved fraction is bioavailable and thus relevant for comparison with laboratory toxicity data. The “total water concentration” according to the WFD captures both the freely dissolved and partly the SOM- and SPM-bound fractions. MEC determined with this approach may thus substantially overestimate freely dissolved concentrations for strongly sorbing chemicals, such as highly hydrophobic substances. This, in turn, may lead to inflated

TU values for these substances and a biased perception of their environmental relevance, particularly when investigating mixture risk drivers. To account for this, we estimated the freely dissolved fraction using predicted log D values (OPERA, pH 7.4, v2.9.2, Mansouri et al., 2018) under typical European river conditions for SPM and DOM. Substances with an estimated freely dissolved fraction below one-third of the total concentration are considered potentially overestimated, as their reported levels may exaggerate their toxicological relevance. In Supplementary Text Section 7, we describe the approach for flagging these substances in detail.

2.6. Construction of a knowledge graph for chemical exposure and hazard data

To integrate environmental exposure data, chemical identifiers, and ecotoxicological hazard information into a unified framework, we constructed a domain-specific knowledge graph that captures the relationships between substances, sites, and species. The graph schema is visualized in Fig. 3A.

The core node types include *Substance*, *Site*, and *Species*. **Substance** nodes represent chemical compounds, uniquely identified by their DTXSID and annotated with alternative identifiers such as CASRN, InChI, and InChIKey. Each substance is also associated with use group annotations derived from regulatory classifications (e.g., REACH) and curated mode-of-action information. **Site** nodes represent the geographic locations at which environmental concentrations were measured. These nodes store spatial metadata, including coordinates (latitude and longitude), water body names, and river basin affiliations. **Species** nodes represent aquatic organisms impacted by chemical exposure, currently including algae, crustaceans (daphnia), and fish. These are further grouped by taxonomic classification (unicellular, invertebrate, and vertebrate).

Edges in the graph describe relationships between these core entities and include rich semantic and quantitative metadata:

- **MEASURED_AT**: Connects a *Substance* to a *Site* and represents environmental concentration measurements. Each relationship instance includes properties such as the measured concentration (mean and median), timepoint (year and quarter), and toxic unit (TU) values computed per species group.
- **TESTED_FOR_TOXICITY**: Connects a *Substance* to a *Species*, indicating the availability of ecotoxicity data. Relationship properties include the toxicity value in mg/L, and, where applicable, a predicted neutral fraction that must be multiplied to the toxicity value if QSAR-based.
- **IS_DRIVER**: Connects a *Substance* to a *Site* to indicate that the substance was identified as a mixture risk driver for a given species group at that site and time. Properties include species affected, temporal metadata, and a numeric importance score. A Boolean flag indicates whether the substance is considered a driver.
- **SUMMARIZED_IMPACT_ON**: Connects a *Site* to a *Species* and stores aggregate metrics such as the sum of toxic units (sumTU), the maximum toxic unit (maxTU), and the ratio of these (ratioTU), which characterizes whether a single or multiple substances drive the observed risk.

The resulting graph captures both direct measurements and derived risk metrics, allowing complex querying across multiple dimensions such as site, time, species, and chemical identity. We stored the graph in a Neo4j graph database, enabling Cypher-based queries and downstream integration with retrieval-augmented language models and visualization tools.

2.7. Computational environment

All computations described in Sections 2.2–2.6 were performed in R version 4.2.3 (2023-03-15). The analysis primarily relied on the tidyverse ecosystem of packages, including dplyr 1.1.2, ggplot2 3.4.3, readr 2.1.4, tibble 3.2.1, tidyr 1.3.0, purrr 1.0.1, forcats 1.0.0, and stringr 1.5.0. Code supporting all analyses is openly available, with repository links provided in the Data & Code availability Section 4.6, ensuring full reproducibility of the results.

2.8. Dockerized knowledge graph for reproducibility

To enhance reproducibility and facilitate access to the integrated knowledge graph, we provide a Docker image containing a pre-loaded Neo4j graph database. The image is based on Neo4j version 5.25.1-community and includes all curated nodes, relationships, and indices used in our analyses. The database was constructed by importing CSV-formatted data into a fresh Neo4j instance, followed by the creation of a database dump, which was embedded in the final Docker image. This setup enables users to launch the containerized database environment with minimal effort and immediate access to the complete dataset. The Docker image, the CSV source files, and the scripts used to generate the image are available via Zenodo and the corresponding Git repository (see the Data and Code Availability section).

3. Results

3.1. Chemical mixture risk driver heterogeneity in European freshwaters determined with an ideal dataset

We initially investigated chemical mixture risk driver heterogeneity in European rivers using the chemical monitoring data provided by Finckh et al. (2024), referred to as Dataset I in Section 2. This data set provides chemical concentration data for 503 chemicals in 445 locations acquired in a single measurement campaign and sampled between 2015 and 2021. Since the same set of chemicals was measured in each location of this data set, mixture risk drivers are comparable between locations. We computed Toxic units (TU) for 494 substances in 433 locations. For 282, 330 and 324 substances curated measured effect concentrations from EcotoxDB were available for algae, crustaceans, and fish, respectively. Upon computing $sumTU$ as an indicator of the total mixture risk 336, 270 and 238 locations exceeded a limit of $sumTU \geq 0.001$ for algae, crustaceans, and fish, respectively, with 359 locations at risk across all species combined (Fig. 2A). See Supplementary Fig. 1A for the spatial distribution of $sumTU$ values across Europe for all three BQEs.

To investigate whether the total mixture risk is driven by a single substance or due to the occurrence of multiple substances jointly, we computed the $ratioTU$ for each location, which is the ratio between the TU of the most toxic substance per location and species group over the $sumTU$ of this location. A $ratioTU$ value close to 1 indicates that the mixture risk at a given location is dominated by a single substance. Conversely, lower $ratioTU$ values reflect a more diverse contribution of multiple substances to the total mixture risk. The distribution of $ratioTU$, stratified by the species group, indicated that only 4.85% to 6% of locations at risk were mainly driven by a single substance, using a threshold of $ratioTU = 0.95$, which corresponds to the 95th percentile of the overall $ratioTU$ distribution. On the contrary, in 26% (= 93) locations at risk, the most toxic substance was responsible for less than 25% of the total risk (Supplementary Figure 1B).

To identify the main drivers of mixture risk, we sorted the substances by descending TU for each location and each species group separately. We subsequently defined those substances as *mixture risk drivers* necessary to yield 75% of $sumTU$ for each location and species group. This approach allows to focus on the locally most important

drivers and reduces the complexity of the data considered in downstream analyses. The specific choice of 75% of $sumTU$ as a cutoff is a tradeoff between reducing complexity further (lowering the cutoff) while missing increasingly important risk-driving substances. Since we provide all data and analysis code, readers may easily pursue an analogous analysis with different cutoff values if desired. Fig. 2B shows the definition of mixture risk drivers at location EUS367 (Danube, Serbia) as an example. Independent of the species group, we identified between one and five mixture risk drivers for most locations at risk (Fig. 2D). For roughly three-quarters of the locations we found two or more drivers, while one location showed up to 18 mixture risk driving chemicals (EUS183).

We termed the ratio between the TU of a mixture risk-driving chemical and the sum of TU of all drivers of a location and species group the *driver importance*. Fig. 2C displays the *driver importance* of all drivers with *driver importance* ≥ 0.1 for all at-risk locations and stratified per species group. We observed that a large set of substances — in total 201 — acted as mixture risk drivers across all locations at risk. Some significant drivers were identified for only one species group. Triclosan, for example, was identified as an important mixture risk driver at many locations for algae, with less importance for crustaceans, and no importance as a mixture risk driver for fish. Bisphenol-S was identified as a frequent mixture risk driver for fish, but hardly for the two other species groups. Sucralose and tributyl phosphate were important mixture risk drivers at many locations across all three species groups. The identified mixture risk drivers include substances from various use categories, such as industrial chemicals, biocides, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, or food additives. See Supplementary Table 1 and Section 9 in the supplement.

3.2. Re-use of NORMAN chemical monitoring data to determine mixture risk

Due to its consistency, the chemical occurrence data provided by Finckh et al. (2024) are ideal for comparing mixture risk drivers between locations. However, despite its 445 locations, the dataset covers only a small fraction of European freshwater bodies and provides measured concentrations only for a single sampling time point per location. Thus, it does not allow for the investigation of the temporal variations of mixture risk drivers.

The Norman EMPODAT database provides the most extensive data collection on measured environmental concentrations of chemicals in European freshwaters (Dulio et al., 2018). Since Norman EMPODAT collects data from many different monitoring efforts, sampling time points, analytical methods, and sets of measured substances vary. Re-using Norman EMPODAT data thus requires special care when performing comparative analyses involving data from different monitoring campaigns. We normalized, curated, and filtered Norman EMPODAT to ensure unique identifiers of locations and water body names, to represent valid coordinates of locations on European freshwater bodies and retained measurements for substances that could be mapped to DTXSIDs (Mutlu et al., 2025). Due to the varying temporal resolution of the data, we computed the median concentration for each chemical per quarter and location for further analyses. These data and further data computed in subsequent steps, together with information on chemicals (dataset chemical_data) and chemical use (dataset chemical_use) were integrated into a knowledge graph—see cartoon in Fig. 3A.

In total, we retrieved measured concentrations for 3771 substances across 12499 locations spanning the quarters for the years 1998 to 2020. A total of 1949 substances were detected at 11106 locations. Although the number of measured substances and included locations increased substantially after 2008, the median and maximum $sumTU$ computed across all locations did not coincide with the years with the highest number of detected substances or included locations (Fig. 3B). Instead, quarters with data of many different locations exhibited comparably lower $median(sumTU)$. This suggests that the observed

Fig. 2. Heterogeneity of freshwater mixture risk drivers determined in an ideal dataset. (A) Distribution of $sumTU$ stratified by BQE. The vertical black solid and dashed lines indicate $sumTU$ of 0.001 and 1, respectively. (B) Mixture risk driving chemicals identified at station EUS367 (Danube, Serbia). (C) Driver importance per location at risk and species group plotted for all chemical mixture risk drivers with $driver\ importance \geq 0.1$. Dot size corresponds to $driver\ importance$, while the color indicates the primary use group of the substances. On the x-axis, the same set of locations is plotted for each species group. A varying dot size along a line corresponds to varying driver importance between locations and between species, respectively. A similar plot showing all identified mixture risk drivers is shown in Supplementary Figure 2. (D) Histogram of the number of mixture risk drivers identified across all locations at risk stratified per species group. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Chemical mixture risk to aquatic species determined by Norman EMPODAT data re-use. (A) Knowledge graph with example data from our integrated data resource to illustrate the relation between sites, substances, and species (nodes) as used in the study and stored in the graph database. (B) Number of locations, number of measured and detected substances, and median and maximum *sumTU* per quarter across all Norman EMPODAT data. (C) Distribution of *sumTU* per species group across all locations and quarters. (D) Spatial distribution of *max(sumTU)* across Europe for species group algae.

elevations in *median(sumTU)* are more a consequence of a less precise median estimate due to less data, potentially combined with individual locations of elevated risk, rather than a general increase of *sumTUs* over many locations.

We investigated the distribution of *sumTU* across locations per species group, either by considering each location–quarter pair (Fig. 3C) or by computing the *max(sumTU)* per location across all quarters (Supplementary Figure 4 A). For algae, crustaceans, and fish 7175, 5701 and 5608 locations exceeded the risk threshold of *sumTU* ≥ 0.001 at least once across all quarters for which data were available. Plotting these *max(sumTU)* values for the species group algae to the European map exhibited some local patterns of high or low-maximal risk, but generally, high- and low-risk locations were located across all of Europe (Fig. 3D). It has been repeatedly suggested that an observed increase in chemical mixture risk might be due to increasingly more sensitive measurement technologies. We did, however, not observe a

clear correlation when plotting *max(sumTU)* against the numbers of measured substances (Supplementary Figure 4 B).

3.3. Cumulative risk is determined by multiple risk-driving substances

Considering only at-risk locations, we computed the minimum and maximum *ratioTU* per location across all quarters (Fig. 4A). 14.9, 14.9 and 15.9 % of locations exhibited a *ratioTU* value of 1.0, which corresponds to the 95th percentile of the overall *ratioTU* distribution, for the three species groups when considering the most single-substance-driven time point via *max(ratioTU)*. These proportions decreased to 6.4, 6.9 and 8.7 % when considering the timepoint at which the total risk was most strongly composed of multiple substances. In summary, in 93.6, 93.1 and 91.3 % of locations, the risk was driven by more than a single driver in at least one of the considered time points. Spatially, this *min(sumTU)* varied considerably between species (Fig. 4B).

Fig. 4. Chemical Mixture risk in European freshwater bodies is determined by multiple risk-driving substances. (A) Distribution of $\max(\text{ratioTU})$, the largest and $\min(\text{ratioTU})$, the smallest ratioTU per location and species-group over time. Since for a specific location, ratioTU varies over quarters, the maximum and minimum for each location are considered here. (B) Spatial distribution of $\min(\text{ratioTU})$ across Europe for all locations at risk. (C) Histogram of the number of mixture risk drivers across locations stratified by the species group. We retained the highest count of drivers per location across all quarters.

Investigating the chemical mixture risk drivers at the time points with the highest driver count showed that the cumulative risk of 53 to 70% of the at-risk locations was driven by two or more substances (Fig. 4C). Five or more substances were contributing to the cumulative chemicals risk in approximately 10, 8 and 8 % for algae, crustaceans, and fish, respectively. To conclude, in the majority of cases mixture risk was driven by multiple substances in a substantial number of European freshwater bodies.

3.4. Chemical mixture risk drivers are heterogeneous, species-specific, and span regulatory domains

Investigating the risk-driving chemicals in more detail, we identified 399, 387 and 367 driver substances for algae, crustaceans, and fish (see

Section 9 in the supplement for a link to the complete list of driver substances). In total, these amounted to 580 distinct substances.

Importantly, in contrast to the ideal dataset analyzed previously, sample preparation and low-level data processing workflows vary considerably within the Norman EMPODAT dataset. This variability has important consequences for the reported concentrations of highly hydrophobic substances, which are predominantly particle-bound in water samples. Reliably measuring the freely dissolved concentrations of highly hydrophobic substances requires passive sampling approaches. In contrast, other approaches, which vary in their removal of particle- and colloidal-bound fractions, along with the inclusion or exclusion of these substances in the list of targeted substances, introduce substantial bias. Since metadata describing the relevant workflow steps, however,

Fig. 5. Most frequent mixture-risk drivers. (A–C) These figures show how frequently the most common drivers were identified for algae, crustaceans, and fish versus how frequently these substances were measured. We removed highly hydrophobic substances for which measured environmental concentrations likely overestimate freely dissolved concentrations when “total water concentration” is reported according to the WFD. The list of most frequent drivers, including these substances with a flag, is displayed in Supplementary Figure 7. (D) All locations identified at risk in the first quarter of 2009 where terbuthylazine, the most frequently observed risk-driver for algae, was identified as a risk-driver (left), was measured, but not a risk-driver (middle), and was not measured at this time point (right). (E) Numbers of at-risk locations at the first quarter of 2009 corresponding to (D).

is not consistently available, this remains an issue in a data re-use approach.

When compiling the list of the most frequently observed mixture risk driving substances for the three BQEs, we observed several highly hydrophobic substances for which we suspected that the MEC could be an overestimate of the freely dissolved concentration. Assuming that many studies in Normandy EMPODAT reported “total water concentrations” according to WFD, we therefore computed the freely dissolved fraction for all driver substances relying on typical contents of SPM and DOC in European rivers (Supplemental Text Section 7). Fig. 5A–C displays the most frequently observed mixture risk driving substances for algae, crustaceans, and fish, respectively, excluding substances for which measured environmental concentrations likely overestimate freely dissolved concentrations. The most frequent drivers,

including these substances with a flag, are displayed in Supplementary Figure 7. Additionally, we included this flag in the table of all drivers per location, linked in Supplemental Text Section 9. For algae, the most frequently observed drivers were the agriculturally widely used herbicides terbuthylazine, diflufenican, diuron, chlorotoluron, and copper. Mixture risk for crustaceans was most frequently driven by copper and zinc, followed by the fungicide carbendazim and the PAHs (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons) pyrene and fluoranthene. For fish, we found copper, zinc, iron, cyanide, and the herbicide and fungicide procymidone to drive mixture risks most frequently. These most frequently observed drivers were also frequently measured substances. However, the number of locations where a substance was measured did not correlate strongly with its rank as a risk driving substance (correlation coefficient is -0.03). Since we only considered at-risk locations,

the number of locations where a substance was measured may vary between the three figures (Fig. 5A–C).

We found 143 mixture risk drivers overlapping between the analysis based on Dataset I and Dataset II. The overlap of these 143 mixture risk drivers across the three BQEs and the corresponding use groups within both datasets is shown in Supplemental Figure 11.

We identified the first quarter of 2009 as the time point when terbuthylazine, the overall most frequently observed chemical risk-driver for algae, acted as a driver in the highest number of locations. Fig. 5D displays at-risk locations where terbuthylazine was identified as a risk-driver at this time point, where terbuthylazine was measured but did not act as a driver, and where terbuthylazine was not measured at this time point. Of all locations that we considered at risk at this time point, terbuthylazine acted as a driver in 54, while it was not measured in 282 (Fig. 5E).

This example illustrates the heterogeneity of the data collected in Norman EMPDAT. Since the database assembles data from various monitoring efforts, the set of investigated substances may differ between campaigns, locations, and time points. This data inconsistency has fundamental consequences if one wants to answer the question of whether or not mixture risk-driving chemicals are heterogeneous between locations. Thus, we needed to ensure that we only compared the heterogeneity of risk-drivers between locations and time points where those chemicals had been consistently measured.

Therefore, we clustered all locations at each quarter based on their Tanimoto Similarities between locations computed on the sets of measured substances. Next, we ensured that all identified mixture-risk-driving substances in a cluster were measured at all locations of the cluster. Subsequently, we removed locations not meeting this criterion from the cluster and compared mixture-risk-driving substances between the locations of a cluster. For algae, crustaceans, and fish, we identified 7251, 7251 and 7258 clusters across all quarters, respectively. In all three BQEs, we found up to 194 clusters within a quarter, and the largest cluster assembled 251 locations.

Some clusters exhibited pronounced heterogeneity between locations: An example is a large cluster identified for algae in France, which contained 532 locations and 37 risk-driving substances (Fig. 6A, B). While several chemicals, e.g., diflufenican, zinc, or copper, were identified as risk drivers for most of the locations in the cluster (323), other substances, e.g., azoxystrobin, a broad-spectrum agriculturally used fungicide, the herbicides bromacil and oxadiazon, or the fungicide propiconazole, used as a PPP in agriculture and as a biocide in wood preservation, were identified to drive the mixture risk only at a few or even at single location of the cluster.

Some clusters showed remarkable differences in risk-driving chemicals identified for the three different species groups. An example is shown in Fig. 6C, D, a cluster where some of the herbicides discussed above were again identified as mixture-risk drivers for algae, and the pharmaceutical digitoxin was identified as mixture-risk drivers exclusively for crustaceans. Several PAHs also displayed species-specific patterns; however, we found that their MECs likely overestimate the freely dissolved concentrations, and we thus flagged them according to the procedure described in Section 7 of the Supplement. The drug primidone was identified as a mixture-risk driver only for fish. Several other substances, such as, e.g., the insecticide and acaricide azinphos-ethyl, the PAH anthracene, or the artificial sweetener sucralose, were identified as mixture-risk drivers for fish, but were also found to be risk-driving for algae and crustaceans at a few locations of this cluster.

3.5. Chemical mixture risk drivers vary over time

We further investigated whether mixture-risk-drivers vary over time. Fig. 7A shows the driver importance plots for a cluster of locations with consistently measured chemical mixture risk drivers for two quarters in 2017. While some chemicals show importance as a mixture risk driver in both time points, e.g., terbuthylazine, linuron

was only important in the earlier time point, and fluoxastrobin was more important in more locations at the later time point, indicating that mixture risk drivers vary over time.

To systematically search for clusters with varying important chemical risk drivers over time, we, in addition to clustering location–quarter pairs by the similarity of measured substances, also clustered the locations by the similarity of identified risk drivers. This allowed us to search for clusters with consistently measured substances over time and diverging risk drivers. Fig. 7B shows exemplarily such a cluster with chemical risk drivers and their driver importance at 11 locations over four time points between 2014 and 2020. In contrast to the previous plots, we faceted this plot by location to allow for easier comparison over time. In this cluster, linuron was an important mixture risk driver in all locations in 2014. It was less important in later years and did not occur in 2020. This pattern can be explained as the authorization of linuron in Europe was revoked in 2017, and application was only allowed until 2018. Azoxystrobin became less important over time in some locations of this cluster, while remaining equally important in others. Diflufenican and terbuthylazine gained in importance over time. This example shows how toxic chemicals change their importance and contributions to chemical mixture risks over time while the locations where identified to be exposed to a cumulative risk at all time points. In summary, we conclude that chemical mixture risk drivers in European freshwater bodies involve a range of substances from different use groups, that vary between locations and over time. These chemicals, regulated and authorized by different regulations and agencies, co-occur as mixtures with varying complexity and mixture risk driver compositions.

4. Discussion

Evidence increases that anthropogenic chemical pollution is one of the key drivers of biodiversity loss, next to land use changes, direct exploitation, invasive species, and climate change (Haase et al., 2025; Oginah et al., 2025). Environmental risk assessment studies of freshwaters that take co-exposures into account consistently conclude that mixtures of chemicals often pose an overall risk that exceeds limit values (Malaj et al., 2014; Finckh et al., 2024; Weisner et al., 2021) while conclusions on the number of risk driving chemicals largely diverge depending on the available and assessed data and the applied risk assessment methodology (Spurgeon et al., 2022; Finckh et al., 2022a, 2024; Beckers et al., 2023).

In this data re-use study, leveraging two different large European chemical monitoring data sets, we aimed to investigate the number and heterogeneity of chemical mixture risk drivers in European freshwaters. Our focus was on reproducibility and FAIRness of data and tools, and on curating and normalizing data to maximize coverage while maintaining high data and analysis quality. Using a graph database, we created a flexible framework for integrating and querying data from multiple sources, enabling adaptation to diverse research questions.

We combined chemical occurrence data from a homogeneous but limited dataset and an extensive highly heterogeneous dataset with curated hazard data for the three regulatory relevant Biological Quality Elements (BQE) according to the WFD, namely algae, crustaceans, and fish, each considered separately. This integration allowed us to analyze chemical mixture risk drivers in European freshwater, assessing their numbers, spatial and temporal heterogeneity, and relevance for the three BQE.

4.1. Aquatic mixture risks result from co-occurrence of many different mixture risk driving chemicals

We found 201 and 580 mixture risk driving substances across all location–time pairs and BQE in the datasets of Finckh et al. (2024) and Norman EMPDAT respectively, with an overlap of 143 substances.

Fig. 6. Risk drivers vary across locations and span different use groups and regulatory domains. (A) Chemical mixture risk-drivers of a selected cluster with 532 locations, displayed with their *driver importance* for species group algae shown as dot size calculated for each location of the selected cluster. The plot illustrates the heterogeneity of mixture-risk-driving-substances across the locations of the cluster. Colors indicate the different use groups of the chemicals. Substances for which we found the MEC to overestimate freely dissolved concentrations are shown in non-bold font, reliable substances in bold. (B) Map of locations corresponding to the cluster displayed in (A). The color key indicates the Tanimoto similarity of each location to the location with highest overall similarity, indicated by a purple diamond, based on the sets of measured substances. (C) Another selected cluster with 67 locations computed analogously to (A) illustrating the heterogeneity of driver substances between locations and species groups. On the x-axis, the same set of locations is plotted for each species group. (D) The respective sampling sites of the cluster shown in (C). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Risk drivers vary over time. (A) This figure displays the driver importance for a cluster of locations at two different time points. The Supplementary Figure 4 displays a map of the locations in this cluster. (B) Driver importance plot for eleven locations of a cluster of consistently measured drivers and four time points between 2014 and 2020.

This finding is in remarkable contrast to several other studies investigating mixture risk drivers in freshwaters, which reported considerably fewer drivers, as detailed in the introduction. Also, there is hardly any overlap between the driver substances reported by these studies (Supplemental Figure 10).

Mixture risk assessment is commonly based on summing ratios between exposure and effect concentrations of co-occurring substances. However, differences in data sources, data curation strategies, analysis protocols, and the absence of a clear definition of the term ‘risk driver,’ can partly explain the pronounced heterogeneity observed in

previous studies. While Rorije et al. (2022) relied on Norman EM-PODAT as we did, they used samples from a different period and removed inconsistent data points that we partially retained following the curation approach in Mutlu et al. (2025). Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023) used monitoring data in the Waterbase database of the European Environment Agency (EEA), and discarded metals prior to mixture risk estimation. Briels et al. (2023) re-analyzed chemical occurrence data from the EauFrance database, merged with data from a surfactant monitoring campaign, and removed metals. Rorije et al. (2022), Spurgeon et al. (2022), Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023), and Briels et al. (2023) used SSDs from Posthuma et al. (2019) as the hazard data source, some of which adopted hazard data for PAHs using the PETROTOX model (Redman et al., 2017). Weichert et al. (2025) used chronic EcotoxDB-data supplemented by a machine learning approach (Gustavsson et al., 2024). In this study, we also relied on curated EcotoxDB data from Kramer et al. (2024), which were supplemented with predicted baseline toxicity values.

The resulting numbers of risk-driving substances depend on their definition and several data analysis parameters. For example, Rorije et al. (2022) classified drivers as substances exceeding specific TU thresholds, Spurgeon et al. (2022) considered the top one or two contributors per sample, and Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023) restricted drivers to those exceeding an ecotoxicological effect limit. In contrast, we defined risk drivers as the most significantly contributing substances, summing up to 75% of the total risk, considering only at-risk locations with a risk threshold of $sumTU > 0.001$. This approach focuses on the most problematic substances locally while avoiding hard TU cutoffs for individual substances. Finckh et al. (2022a) employed a related approach that sorts substances by TU and considers all substance drivers except those with the smallest TU, which sum up to the risk cutoff. While this procedure is robust when using data from a consistent measurement campaign, it is limited in a data re-use approach with varying sets of measured substances.

We performed sensitivity analyses for the $sumTU$ threshold and the proportion of total risk explained by drivers threshold (Supplement Sections 5 and 8). We found that the set of drivers remained large for all investigated thresholds. For example, even for a highly relaxed threshold of $sumTU \geq 0.1$, we identified more than 100 risk-driving substances (Supplementary Figure 8). Since we provide all analysis code and data in public repositories, readers can seamlessly reproduce our results and vary parameters for additional or further analyses.

4.2. Complex patterns and spatial heterogeneity of mixture risk drivers across European freshwater bodies

Our analyses revealed complex patterns of mixture-risk-driving substances that challenge simplistic regulatory approaches. For both chemical occurrence datasets, we found that chemical mixture risks in European freshwater ecosystems were driven by heterogeneous sets of substances that varied substantially across locations, time, and species groups. Using the Finckh et al. (2024) dataset we found that mixture risks were predominantly driven by a single substance in only 6% to 7% of the sites at risk, while in the majority of locations, the most toxic substance was responsible for less than 25% of the total risk. Our analysis of the more extensive Norman EMPODAT dataset corroborated these findings, with approximately two-thirds of at-risk locations being driven by two or more substances, considering the time point where the respective risk-driving chemical had the highest count. This pattern applied to all three BQEs, indicating a broad ecological significance of the risk posed by multiple substance co-occurrence. These observations differ markedly from Rodea-Palomares et al. (2023), who reported that only 0.8% to 8.3% of the sites with significant mixture risks (identified as site-year combinations) had two or more risk driving substances. In a similar analysis excluding metals, Briels et al. (2023), reported 9% of mixtures with significant risks in this category. Rorije et al. (2022),

also utilizing Norman EMPODAT, found that 31% of at-risk locations had more than one chemical driving the mixture risk.

A key finding of our study is the pronounced spatial heterogeneity of mixture risk drivers. The cluster analysis revealed that even within spatially proximate regions, the specific substances driving mixture risks can vary substantially between locations. For example, in the French cluster (Fig. 6A), substances like diflufenican, zinc, and copper were identified as mixture risk drivers for algae across most locations. In contrast, azoxystrobin, bromacil, oxadiazon, and propiconazole were identified as mixture risk drivers at only a few specific sites. Comparable spatial heterogeneity patterns have been noted in some previous studies (e.g., Briels et al., 2023; Rodea-Palomares et al., 2023), although often at a lower resolution or with fewer driver substances identified, likely reflecting differences in datasets, driver definitions, and analytical approaches. The spatial heterogeneity likely reflects differences in land use patterns, point source emissions, and hydrological characteristics that influence the composition of chemical mixtures at specific locations. It suggests that effective management of chemical mixture risks requires site-specific considerations to address the unique combination of mixture risk-driving substances at each location, in addition to global approaches such as a mixture assessment factor.

4.3. Regulatory implications for mixture risk-driving substances belonging to different chemical classes

The mixture risk-driving substances identified in this study span various chemical classes and regulatory domains, including industrial chemicals, metals, biocides, PPPs, pharmaceuticals, and food additives. For algae, agricultural herbicides such as terbuthylazin, diflufenican, and diuron were identified as predominant risk drivers, which reflects their specific modes of action in targeting photosynthetic organisms. In contrast, for crustaceans and fish, metals such as copper and zinc, and the no longer authorized fungicide carbendazim were among the most frequent mixture risk drivers. The set of mixture risk drivers also contained several PAHs, such as benzo[ghi]perylene and benz[a]anthracene, which we flagged because we considered the MEC to overestimate the freely dissolved concentration. There are, however, several lower molecular weight PAHs among the drivers, like pyrene, for which we found the MEC to estimate freely dissolved concentrations reliably (see also 4.5).

When considering the overlap of all risk drivers identified in both Datasets, we found that most fall into the use categories of industrial chemicals, pharmaceuticals, biocides, and PPPs, with food additives playing only a minor role. We identified considerable overlap between the three BQEs, particularly for certain metals and widely used biocides and PPPs. However, many drivers are specific to a single BQE, highlighting the need for management approaches that address both broadly relevant and BQE-specific drivers (Supplemental Figure 11).

The diversity of risk-driving substances across chemical classes has important implications for chemical regulation. Current regulatory frameworks are largely compartmentalized by chemical use (e.g., PPPs, biocides, pharmaceuticals), which may hinder adequate protection of the freshwater ecosystems from chemical mixture risks that transcend these artificial regulatory boundaries.

Our results clearly demonstrate that aquatic mixture risks are not driven by a small set of consistently identifiable substances but by a large, heterogeneous set of drivers that vary between sites, species, and time. This empirical evidence directly supports the rationale of the European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (European Commission, 2020), which explicitly calls for improved protection against combined chemical exposures. In particular, our findings provide scientific support for the introduction of a mixture allocation factor (MAF) under REACH (Backhaus, 2023; Treu et al., 2024). By accounting for cumulative risks across regulatory domains, the MAF would address the ecological reality that freshwater mixture risks cannot be managed through the regulation of a few priority pollutants alone. In this sense,

our study substantiates that the CSS represents a necessary paradigm shift: moving from single-substance and single-regulation approaches towards integrated strategies that reflect the true complexity of mixture risks in European freshwaters.

4.4. Advancing data accessibility through knowledge graphs

Our Neo4j-based knowledge graph offers a practical and reusable framework for integrating heterogeneous environmental data, including measured concentrations, chemical identifiers, and hazard information. By publishing the graph in a containerized format, we ensure immediate accessibility and reproducibility. The container let researchers directly explore, query, and build upon the curated data without an additional setup. This approach supports transparency and interoperability and encourages data re-use and collaborative refinement. More broadly, it illustrates how knowledge graphs can facilitate the integration of fragmented datasets and support hypothesis generation, thereby contributing to more informed and holistic assessments in environmental sciences. Finally, we note that the application of knowledge graphs in environmental toxicology is gaining traction, particularly for integrating heterogeneous datasets and supporting semantic queries, e.g., Myklebust et al. (2019), Bub et al. (2025).

4.5. Methodological considerations, limitations, and implications

The methodological design of our study emphasizes the importance of harmonized data processing, integration, and analysis workflows in environmental risk assessment. While using a graph database enables scalable data management and interoperability, several domain-specific considerations shaped the interpretation of our findings.

A key difference between Dataset I and Dataset II is the presence of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the latter. This discrepancy stems from methodological differences in sampling and chemical analysis. Dataset I (Finckh et al., 2024) excluded highly hydrophobic substances and directly injected water samples. In contrast, Dataset II (Norman EMPODAT) aggregates measurements from diverse studies with varying experimental protocols, low-level data processing, and target substance lists. When highly hydrophobic substances, such as PAHs, are analyzed using whole-water extraction, reported concentrations may substantially overestimate freely dissolved concentrations, as explained in Section 7 of the Supplement in more detail. Since metadata describing these workflow steps in sufficient detail is often missing, we cannot easily accommodate for these differences in a data re-use approach. We assumed that many studies in Norman EMPODAT reported “total water concentrations” according to WFD and therefore computed the freely dissolved fraction for all driver substances relying on typical contents of SPM and DOC in European rivers (Supplemental Text Section 7). We subsequently flagged these substances to emphasize that their relevance in mixture toxicity should be considered with caution. While PAHs are well-studied toxicants, their environmental bioavailability and thus their role in mixture toxicity are subject to complex processes such as sorption and partitioning behavior, e.g., Berríos-Rolón et al. (2025). As a result, their identification as drivers in mixture risk assessment based on total water concentrations warrants cautious interpretation. Future work could address this by training machine learning classifiers to infer the likely sampling protocol from chemical occurrence patterns, enabling a more elaborate flagging of concentrations of highly hydrophobic substances where overestimation is probable.

Beyond methodological harmonization, our study highlights limitations and opportunities in hazard data availability. The ability to robustly identify mixture risk drivers depends not only on high-quality exposure data but also on comprehensive hazard information. However, hazard datasets remain incomplete for many substances, particularly for chronic endpoints and less-studied taxa. Recent advances in predictive ecotoxicology, such as the machine-learning approaches described

by Gustavsson et al. (2024) offer promising strategies to fill these gaps. Integrating such predictive models into workflows like ours could expand chemical coverage, but careful validation is required to ensure reliability.

Our findings have implications for chemical monitoring strategies in aquatic ecosystems. Current monitoring programs often focus on a predefined list of substances based on historical concerns or regulatory requirements. Our results indicate that this approach may miss many substances that drive mixture risks at specific locations. For example, terbuthylazine, the most frequently observed risk driver for algae, was not measured at almost as many sites as those where it was measured. These conclusions are supported by a recently published, extensive analysis of US chemical monitoring data, which reported that a large fraction of environmentally relevant chemicals lacks sufficient monitoring and, to a lesser extent, toxicity data, resulting in significant bias in the risk perception of environmental chemicals (Bub et al., 2025).

The identified heterogeneity of chemical mixture risk drivers across sites suggests that more comprehensive monitoring strategies are needed that can capture the full range of substances contributing to mixture risks or, at least, the frequently observed risk-driving substances. Such strategies include broader screening of chemicals from various use classes and regulatory domains, targeted monitoring informed by local land use and known emission sources, or a combination of non-target screening and targeted monitoring. Finally, reporting and documentation of monitoring data should consider machine-readable sample metadata to further reduce analysis biases in the future.

Beyond methodological aspects, our findings have strong practical implications for water governance. The heterogeneity and species-specificity of mixture risk drivers demonstrate that freshwater protection strategies cannot rely on static lists of priority pollutants. Instead, adaptive monitoring schemes are required that flexibly capture locally relevant drivers, including pesticides with pronounced seasonal application patterns. Importantly, the observed heterogeneity also has a trans-boundary dimension: pesticides applied in one country may act as major mixture risk drivers downstream in another. This underscores the need for cross-border data sharing and coordinated pesticide regulation to prevent pollution transfer across jurisdictions. Strengthening international cooperation is therefore critical to implement monitoring and regulatory approaches that match the ecological reality of European freshwater systems (Huang and Li, 2025; Tang et al., 2025).

The results presented here also underscore the need to adapt biodiversity assessment frameworks. Current approaches under the Water Framework Directive primarily infer ecological status from biological quality elements without explicitly accounting for the site- and species-specific impacts of complex chemical mixtures. The pronounced heterogeneity of mixture risk drivers implies that chemical pressures can contribute to stalled or incomplete biodiversity recovery even where classical stressors are managed (Haase et al., 2023). Linking mixture risk metrics (e.g., sumTU and risk driver profiles) to biodiversity indicators would improve attribution of observed ecological change to chemical pressures and help prioritize conservation actions (Haase et al., 2025). Evidence from multiple-stressor syntheses shows that chemical stressors can alter biodiversity and ecosystem functioning on par with other global pressures. (Brauns et al., 2022). Consequently, mixture exposures should be explicitly incorporated into frameworks for assessing biodiversity status and trends.

4.6. Conclusions

Our analysis of chemical mixture risks in European freshwater bodies demonstrates that heterogeneous sets of substances that vary across locations, time, and taxonomic groups drive these risks. This finding challenges previous assertions that a small, consistent set of substances drives mixture risks and underlines the need for broader regulatory approaches to safeguard freshwater ecosystems from mixture risks.

The diverse chemical classes identified as risk drivers — including industrial chemicals, PPPs, pharmaceuticals, metals, and other contaminants — highlight the need for integrated regulatory approaches that transcend the individual chemical regulatory frameworks.

The identified spatial heterogeneity of chemical mixture risk drivers underlines that effective management of chemical exposures requires both, broader regulatory frameworks, but also targeted approaches informed by local conditions. Our findings provide empirical support for political or regulatory initiatives like the European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability or the implementation of a MAF under REACH, aiming at better protection of humans and ecosystems from the combined effects of co-occurring chemicals.

Future research should improve our understanding of the impact of chemical mixture risks on ecosystem health through more comprehensive monitoring of chemical occurrence, better characterization of substance toxicity across different taxonomic groups, and data-driven linkages between ecological and chemical assessments.

In conclusion, the heterogeneity and complexity of chemical mixture risk drivers in European freshwater bodies necessitate a paradigm shift in monitoring, assessing, and regulating chemicals to protect aquatic ecosystems. Rather than focusing on a small set of key pollutants, adequate environmental protection requires comprehensive approaches that account for the cumulative impact of multiple substances across diverse taxonomic groups and the unique combinations of substances driving risks at specific locations.

Data & code availability

All data and materials supporting this study are openly available:

The containerized knowledge graph, based on Neo4j and containing all integrated exposure, chemical, and hazard data, is archived on Zenodo together with a container deployment guide and additional links: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14616124> Supplementary CSV files, including driver substance tables and metadata referenced in the manuscript and supplementary document, are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15804639>

A publicly accessible conversational agent, EcoToxFred (Scheibe and Schor, 2025), allows natural language querying of the knowledge graph and supports interactive exploration of the dataset: <https://ecotoxfred.web.app.ufz.de/>. EcoToxFred demonstrates the potential of large language models grounded in structured graph data for transparent, queryable access to ecotoxicological information. It highlights a novel interface for human–AI collaboration in environmental research and regulatory contexts.

The complete analysis code for both datasets is openly accessible in the public GitLab repository at https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/department-computational-biology/analysis_code/cheos_data_analysis.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jana Schor: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tobias Schulze:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation. **Nadin Ulrich:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation. **İlhan Mutlu:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Data curation. **Martin Krauss:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Conceptualization. **Werner Brack:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Triet Doan:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sven Bingert:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jan Bumberger:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Wibke Busch:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology,

Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jörg Hackermüller:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Grammarly and Anthropic Claude in order to improve style and correctness of text. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109881>.

Data availability

All data, code, and materials supporting this study are openly available.

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